

Assessment of Risk of Malignancy Index Scoring and Histopathological Correlation in the Diagnosis and Management of Adnexal MassPreeti Pushpam¹, Vidya Paul², Seema³¹Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Laheriasarai, Bihar²Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Laheriasarai, Bihar³Professor and HOD, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Laheriasarai, Bihar

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Vidya Paul

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Adnexal mass pathologies are mostly benign. Given the extremely low five-year survival rate of adnexal malignant tumors, early detection is imperative. There isn't a single, gold-standard investigation that can be used to diagnose adnexal cancer. The menopausal status (M), ultrasound scores (U), and serum CA 125 (U/ML) is combined to create the Risk of Malignancy Index (RMI) scoring system. The purpose of this research is to evaluate how well the Risk of Malignancy Index-3 (RMI-3) scoring system distinguishes between benign and malignant adnexal masses in order to aid in the early detection and treatment of malignant ovarian masses.

Methods: This is a prospective, observational study conducted from June 2019 to May 2020 at Obstetrics and Gynaecology department of Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Bihar, among 50 female patients over the age of 25 who had been diagnosed with an adnexal mass. Each study participant underwent a comprehensive clinical examination, an in-depth history taking, an abdominal and pelvic ultrasonography, and indicators such CA 125. A correlation was established between the Risk of Malignancy Index and the histopathological (HPE) results of the removed tumors.

Results: When the RMI score of 149.2 is used as the cutoff point for diagnosing malignancy, the results show a 92.3% specificity, 79.2% sensitivity, 90.47% positive predictive value, 82.78% negative predictive value, and 86.01% diagnostic accuracy.

Conclusion: The Risk of Malignancy Index score is a straightforward diagnostic tool that can be used as an effective screening tool to separate malignant lesions from adnexal masses.

Keywords: RMI, Adnexal mass, CA 125.

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Introduction

Adnexa is the area next to the uterus containing ligaments, vessels, fallopian tubes, ovaries. [1] Adnexal masses are the growth near the uterus, usually in the ovary or fallopian tube. Adnexal masses include commonly the ovarian cysts, ectopic (tubal) pregnancies, and tumours (benign or malignant). [2]

Adnexal masses are the fourth most common gynaecological cause for hospitalisation and 90% have benign characteristics. Risk of malignancy found to be 13% in premenopausal women and 45% in postmenopausal women. [3,4] Adnexal masses represent a spectrum of conditions from gynaecological and non-gynaecological sources. They may be benign or malignant. The initial detection and evaluation of an adnexal mass requires a high index of suspicion. Appropriate lab

and radiographic studies are required. [5] The most common symptoms reported are abdominal pain, abdomen distension, bloating, urinary urgency, incontinence, weight loss. This requires further evaluation if it persists for more than 2 weeks or failure to respond to appropriate therapy. The risk increases with age, with greater risks after menopause. Most of the patients present in an advanced stage for which 5 year survival rate remains very low.

Hence, it is important to discriminate between benign and malignant nature of the adnexal mass at an earlier stage. [6,7] Non-malignant adnexal masses can be managed, however prepubertal and postmenopausal women with adnexal masses should be evaluated earlier for a better prognosis. Hence, the goal is to differentiate between benign

and malignant masses. CA-125 is used as a screening tool for ovarian malignancy, elevated in almost 80% of ovarian cancer. [8] CA-125 is a non-specific marker for ovarian malignancy, also elevated in other malignancies (endometrial cancer, germ cell tumour, cervical cancer, breast cancer, colon cancer, pancreatic cancer), pregnancy, pelvic inflammatory diseases, adenomyosis etc., It is found to be elevated in 1% of normal females. CA-125 levels less than 35 are considered to be within the normal limit. [8]

The sensitivity of CA 125 value is low. Not all malignant ovarian cancer was associated with elevated CA 125. It is useful for predicting the recurrence of ovarian tumour at earliest and in predicting the treatment effectiveness of patients undergoing chemotherapy for ovarian cancer.

Risk of malignancy index (RMI) is a parameter which is simple, easy to use, practical and highly sensitive, and more specific.

Risk of Malignancy Index is calculated from the three parameters by the following formula, "RMI=U × M × CA 125".

Risk of Malignancy Index (RMI) scoring system, combines the Serum CA 125(U/ML), Ultrasound score (U) and the menopausal status (M).

Materials and Methods

This Prospective, observational study was conducted on 50 female patients diagnosed with adnexal mass under the department of obstetrics and gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Bihar from June 2019 to May 2020. Female patients age above 25 years, both premenopausal and post-menopausal women and all symptomatic individual diagnosed to have adnexal mass were included in this study. Patients age less than 25, pregnant women, patient on peritoneal dialysis, who are not willing to give

informed consent and asymptomatic individuals were excluded in this study.

All the study participants were subjected to detailed history taking, thorough clinical examination, ultrasonogram of abdomen and pelvis, and markers such as CA 125. After pre-op evaluation, patients were taken up for surgery. Other investigations, such as complete blood count, Random blood sugar, renal function test, liver function test and histopathology were done.

Menopausal statuses were assessed. M=1 if premenopausal M=3 if postmenopausal. Serum CA-125 and Ultrasound examination were performed.

A total ultrasound score U was calculated for each patient after assessing all 5 parameters. Ultrasound score was assigned U=1 if 0 or 1 criteria fulfilled and ultrasound score U=3 if 2 or more criteria fulfilled. RMI was calculated for all the patients.

Preoperative assessment was done for all patients. After a thorough preoperative evaluation and aesthetic fitness an informed written consent was obtained and the patients were taken up for laparotomy. After surgery, histopathological (HPE) findings of the excised tumours were analysed in order to determine the final diagnosis. Post-operative follow up were done at 3/6/12 month.

Data was entered in MS excel sheet and analysed using SPSS software version 20.

P-values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results

Results of the study, on efficiency of Risk of Malignancy Index (RMI) scoring system in discriminating benign and malignant adnexal mass compared to the histopathological results, is discussed.

Table 1: The mean age (years) among the subjects was 48.76 (±13.06) years ranging from 23 to 72 years

Age(years)	
Mean	48.76
Median	50
Std.Deviation	13.06
Range	49
Minimum	23
Maximum	72

Table 2: Among the subjects, 14 (28%) had ≤ 40 years followed by 14 (28%) had > 40 years and least 10 (20%) had > 60 years

Age group	No. of cases	Percentage
≤40 years	14	28%
41-50 years	12	24%
51-60 years	14	28%
>60 years	10	20%
Total	50	100%

Table 3: Menopausal score-among the subjects, 25 (50%) had score 1 and 25 (50%) had score 3

Menopausal Score	No. of cases	Percentage
1	25	50%
3	25	50%
Total	50	100%

Table 4: USG score-among the subjects, 27 (54%) had score 3 and 23 (46%) had score 1

USG score	No. of cases	Percentage
1	23	46%
3	27	54%
Total	50	100%

Table 5: CA 125- The mean CA-125 level among the subjects was 77.81 (\pm 95.44) ranging from 4.5 to 350 U/m

CA-125 level (U/ml)	
Mean	77.81
Median	32
Std.Deviation	95.44
Range	345.5
Minimum	4.5
Maximum	350

Table 6: RMI Score- The mean RMI score among the subjects was 487.43 (\pm 793.37) ranging from 4.5 to 3150

RMI score	
Mean	487.43
Median	117.5
Std.Deviation	793.37
Range	3145.5
Minimum	4.5
Maximum	3150

Table 7: Among the subjects, 14 (28%) had Serous Cystadenoma Carcinoma followed by 7 (14%) had Benign Serous Cystadenoma and least 1 (2%) had Clearcell Tumour

Histopathological diagnosis	No. of cases	Percentage
Benign Serous	7	14%
Cyst adenoma		
Clear cell Tumour	1	2%
Dermoid Cyst	3	6%
Endometrioid Adeno	3	6%
Carcinoma		
Endometrioma	1	2%
Fibroma	1	2%
Fibrothecoma	2	4%
Follicular Cyst	4	8%
Granulosa Cell Tumour	1	2%
Mature Cystic Teratoma	2	4%
Mucinous Cyst adenoma	5	10%
Mucinous Cyst adenoma	4	8%
Carcinoma		
Serous Cystadenoma	2	4%
Serous Cystadenoma	14	28%
Carcinoma		
Total	50	100%

Table 8: Among the subjects, 26 (52%) had Benign and 24 (48%) had Malignant tumours

Tumour type	No. of cases	Percentage
Malignant	24	48%
Benign	26	52%
Total	50	100%

Table 9: Comparison of age group with the tumour type

Age group	Tumour type		Total	Fisher exact p value
	Malignant	Benign		
≤40 years	3 (21.42%)	11(78.57%)	14(100%)	0.01
41-50 years	7 (58.33%)	5 (41.66%)	12(100%)	
51-60 years	7(50%)	7(50%)	14(100%)	
>60 years	7(70%)	3(30%)	10(100%)	
Total	24(48%)	26(52%)	50(100%)	

Table 10: The mean RMI score among Malignant was 953.52 (±949.17) which is higher by 896.33 and statistically significant compared to 57.19 (±61.56) in Benign

Tumour Type	No.	Mean	Std. dev.	Mean diff.	p-value by "t" test
Malignant	24	953.52	949.17	896.330	0.001
Benign	26	57.19	61.56		

Table 11:

Test Result Variable(s)	Cutoff	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	Accuracy
	241.50	75.%	100.00%	100.00%	81.25%	88%
RMI score	149.20	79.20%	92.30%	90.47%	82.78%	86.01%
	111.50	83.30%	76.90%	76.90%	83.30%	79.97%

Discussion

The study population comprise of 50 female patients above the age of 25 years, diagnosed with adnexal mass under the Department of obstetrics and gynaecology, DMCH, Laheriasarai, Bihar.

Menopausal Score was among the subjects, 25 (50%) had score 1 and 25 (50%) had score 3. USG score were among the subjects, 27 (54%) had score 3 and 23 (46%) had score 1, CA-125 level was the mean CA-125 level among the subjects was 77.81 (±95.44) ranging from 4.5 to 350 U/ml, RMI score were the mean RMI score among the subjects was 487.43 (±793.37) ranging from 4.5 to 3150 and histopathological diagnosis was among the subjects, 26 (52%) had Benign and 24 (48%) had Malignant tumours. Among the subjects, 14 (28%) had Serous Cystadenoma Carcinoma followed by 7 (14%) had Benign Serous Cystadenoma and least 1 (2%) had Clear cell Tumour.

Comparison of menopausal Score with the tumour

Type was 32% of the subjects with score 1 were malignant type which is lower compared to subjects with score 3 of whom 64% were malignant type and the difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), USG score with the tumour type was 17.39% of the subjects with score 1 were malignant type which is lower compared to subjects with score 3 of whom 74.07% were malignant type and

the difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), RMI score with tumour type: The mean RMI score among Malignant lesions, which was 953.52 (±949.17) which is higher by 896.33 and statistically significant compared to 57.19 (±61.56) in Benign lesions.

The area under the curve for RMI score in predicting malignancy is 0.905(0.819 - 0.991). When the cutoff of RMI score for predicting malignancy is 241.5 which had a sensitivity of 75%, specificity of 100%, positive predictive value of 100%, negative predictive value of 81.25% and a diagnostic accuracy of 88%. When the cutoff of RMI score for predicting malignancy is 111.5 which had a sensitivity of 83.3%, specificity of 76.9%, positive predictive value of 76.9%, negative predictive value of 83.3% and a diagnostic accuracy of 79.97%. When the cutoff of RMI score for predicting malignancy is 149.2 which had a sensitivity of 79.2%, specificity of 92.3%, positive predictive value of 90.47%, negative predictive value of 82.78% and a diagnostic accuracy of 86.01%.

By using Binomial regression, for each unit increase in RMI score, the odds of getting malignancy increases by 1.01 times which is statistically significant.

Conclusion

Compared to Benign lesions, which had a mean RMI score of 57.19 (± 61.56), Malignant lesions had a mean RMI value of 953.52 (± 949.17), which was significantly higher. When predicting malignancy, the RMI score's area under the ROC curve is 0.905 (0.819-0.991). When the RMI score of 149.2 is used as the cutoff point for diagnosing malignancy, the results show a 92.3% specificity, 79.2% sensitivity, 90.47% positive predictive value, 82.78% negative predictive value, and 86.01% diagnostic accuracy. Risk of Malignancy Index score is a simple tool, with a good diagnostic accuracy; hence it can be used as good screening tool for identification of the malignant lesions from the adnexal mass.

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